

The 1st Forum of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society

The Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society (Academy) gathers our most famous scientists and experts from various fields of medicine and dentistry. During the 46 years of its activity, the Academy has held over 850 scientific and educational meetings, a large number of lecture cycles for the general population at the Ilija M. Kolarac Endowment, it has published dozens of monographs and thus contributed to the promotion of the scientific and professional work of distinguished members of the Academy, as well as to the education of doctors and the popularization of science.

On March 24, 2023, the Academy will organize the *1st Forum of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society*. It will be a scientific meeting where the research results of the members of the Academy and their coworkers will be presented and discussed with the aim of promoting their scientific work and realizing their better cooperation in subsequent studies. The topic of the *1st Forum of the Academy* is "Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment and Control of Mass Infectious and Non-Infectious Diseases." It has been our opinion that such a broad topic would attract experts from various fields and thus illustrate the wide-ranging field of scientific interest and work of the Academy members.

Twenty-four papers have been submitted for the *1st Forum of the Academy*. The greatest attention is paid to COVID-19. The results and experiences of the clinical presentation, course, treatment, and outcome of the disease are presented, as well as the results of experimental research and presentations of various post-COVID disorders. These results and experiences are valuable guideposts for planning measures in future epidemics that infectologists and epidemiologists have been warning us about.

In addition to COVID-19, lectures will also be delivered on some important infectious diseases that are not given enough attention, and which can seriously threaten health and life. These are, above all, tuberculosis and fungal diseases, which will be discussed by our well-known experts.

The meeting dedicated to mass diseases could not but include lectures on malignant diseases. Significant results of the study of modern drugs will be presented, as well as research of insufficiently studied tumors that require additional education of doctors, especially concerning the diagnosis of these diseases.

At the Forum, there will be an opportunity to find out the results of clinical and experimental studies on cardiovascular diseases, such as pharmacogenetic studies and analyses of the results of modern methods of cardiovascular diseases treatment.

Studies from the field of dentistry confirm that modern research requires a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach, which has made it possible to achieve exceptional progress in the treatment of oral and dental diseases.

In addition to the presentation from the aforementioned fields, results from ophthalmology, anesthesiology, and otorhinolaryngology will also be presented. The wide range of topics and the quality of submitted abstracts confirm that Academy members contribute significantly to professional and scientific work and the continuous progress of all fields of medicine.

We hope that at the *1st Forum of the Academy*, doctors from different specialties, as well as experts from other related fields, will gather and that a lively discussion will contribute to the quality of the meeting. We wish to all the participants that the Forum fulfills the expectations of us all – the organizers, the authors of the presented studies, and the audience – and that it will be an incentive for the Academy Forum to become a regular annual scientific meeting of the Academy.

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Conclusion TiNx nanocoatings in combination with Cu or Ag nanocoatings possess very important barrier and antimicrobial properties, which are extremely relevant in the development of new medical implants in dentistry and orthopedics.

Keywords: cathodic arc evaporation; DC magnetron sputtering; nanocoatings; ellipsometry; XRD

Conflict of interest: None declared.

Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest before and after the COVID-19 pandemic – a comparison

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Introduction/Objective Pandemic coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused much disruption in the functioning of health care systems throughout the world. As a consequence, significant deterioration of health of the population was observed. The aim of this study was to determine if the COVID-19 pandemic affected management of cardiac arrest (CA) and the survival rate of patients with out-of-hospital CA (OHCA) in this area.

Methods An observational before-and-after study was carried out to determine the effects of COVID-19 pandemic on the survival of patients with OHCA, who were given cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) by the emergency medical services (EMS) teams. The study was conducted between 1 March 2018 and 1 March 2022, with two equal observation periods: prior to the outbreak of the pandemic (Group I) and after it (Group II).

Results A total of 958 patients formed Group I (434 pts; 45.30%) and Group II (524 pts; 54.64%) ($p < 0.05$). No significant difference was found for age, sex, time of arrival of the EMS teams, initial rhythm and adrenaline administration between them. However, patients in Group I were more often intubated ($\chi^2=8.737$; $df=3$; $p=0.033$). Moreover, amiodarone ($\chi^2=6.508$; $df=1$; $p=0.011$) and saline solution ($\chi^2=5.510$; $df=1$; $p=0.019$) were administered to relatively more patients in this group. Return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) and prehospital survival rates were significantly higher in Group I (18.4%) than in Group II (12.6%) ($\chi^2=5.685$; $df=1$; $p=0.017$).

Conclusion The COVID-19 pandemic led to an increase of OHCA. ROSC and prehospital survival rates were higher in the prepandemic period. The management of OHCA by EMS teams may have affected the results.

Keywords: coronavirus disease 2019; cardiopulmonary resuscitation; sudden cardiac arrest; survival

Conflict of interest: None declared.
